

Impulse versus Pressure or Quantum Versus Classical in Reflection / Refraction

Part II Discontinuity in Time

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Newtonian mechanics deals with smoothness in time and space through $x(t)$ where the “details” occur within dx and dt which tend to zero. Thus there are no discontinuities in x and t . We have argued that the quantum free particle wavefunction pieces $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ deal with discontinuities and that smoothness is due to a “modulus” of two dimensional probability e.g. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ which yields 1 or determinism. Both $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ contain finite measures in time and space, namely \hbar/E and \hbar/p and so there may be discontinuities. For example, $\exp(ipx)$ contains probability $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ within a wavelength so $x=vt$ is only an average type of motion. Thus using $\exp(ipx)$ in a problem may result in time discontinuities because the particle is not moving as $x=vt$ within a wavelength.

In Part I we examined one-dimensional reflection/refraction of light from an interface of two media with $n_1=1$ and $n_2>n_1$. We concluded that the quantum solution of this problem involves two equations, one linked to probabilities and the other to impulse. Multiplying the two equations together (with a special grouping, namely a spatial grouping) yields a single equation which may either be interpreted as a pressure balance equation. Thus one starts with two equations which are both grouped in time, but with the second demonstrating vector directions and obtain a single equation which is only grouped in space (which is linked with spatial grouping). By rearranging this equation, one may obtain a time grouping i.e. energy conservation equation, but the two groupings cannot exist together. This is the problem with the classical pressure picture linked to a steady state scenario and not a single photon process which displays a discontinuity in time i.e. a single photon may either reflect or refract.

In this note we try to consider why classical energy conservation/ pressure balance only leads to one equation, while the quantum mechanical approach leads to the two required equations at the price of introducing a square root flux type of probability. We argue that there seem to be two factors. First there is the notion of scalars and vectors and a space versus time picture. The single conservation of energy equation $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where AA, BB, CC represent the incident, reflected and refracted beams is expressed in terms of time and so vector information (i.e. $-p$ for the reflected beam is not conveyed). If one rewrites this as $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ then one obtains a pressure balance type of equation, but time is removed and one is grouping by space.

The second and more important feature we argue is time discontinuity. If one considers a single photon, it may reflect or refract, but not both. Thus there is a time period in which to observe both reflection and refraction and more than one incident photon is needed. Newtonian mechanics in the form of steady state treats time as smooth and so everything must happen instantaneously. This is the idea behind pressure. One considers an impulse $2p$ multiplied by flux i.e. velocity. The flux is used to find the number of particles which strike a surface per second as if this were a continuous smooth process in time. For the case of reflection/refraction it is not. It is discontinuous because either a reflected or a refracted photon is created each time.

Thus the notion of pressure averages this over and loses some of the information in the problem. This, we argue, is why a pressure balance/ energy conservation equation is not sufficient to solve the reflection/refraction problem even though pressure is a physical concept and may be measured (on average) just as $x=vt$ may be measured on average.

The Notion of Information and Reflection/Refraction

Consider a photon which moves in the positive x direction with momentum p and velocity c . At $x=0$ it strikes an interface between a medium with $n_1=1$ and n_2 where $n_2>n_1$. It has a probability to reflect or to refract. Thus there is a discontinuity in time. Both events cannot occur at the same time for a single photon. For a beam of particles, however, some may reflect and others refract at the same time so to speak. Thus the idea of a smooth time process only applies to many photons, not a single photon. Nevertheless, the basic idea of a probability to reflect and refract exists at the level of a single photon and does not require the notion of a beam. This scenario involves discontinuity in time.

Consider the steady state beam situation. In such a case, one may consider a conservation of energy using the notion of flux as one usually does in many particle scenarios. Then:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

Here AA, BB, CC represent the incident, reflected and refracted fluxes. AA etc is written to show that intensity is strictly positive. Velocities appear in this smooth time picture. Everything seems to be fine except for two problems. First, there are two unknowns B, C (if written in terms of A) and only one equation. Secondly, $((1))$ does not show that the reflected beam moves in the negative x direction. This is basic information in the problem and there is no reason why it should be lost. Thus $((1))$ is a scalar type of equation which deals with two regions in time even though physically the incident and reflected beams exist in the spatial region while the refracted exists in another. One may rewrite $((1))$ as:

$$AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2 \quad ((2))$$

Given $E= |p|c$, $1/c$ may be replaced with $|p|/E$, but E is the same for A, B, C and cancels out so:

$$AA |p| - BB|p| = CC|p_2| \quad ((3))$$

AA is a flux/intensity and so contains c , thus $AA|p|$ contains $|p|c$, but this is impulse times speed which is used in the calculation of pressure. (Here $|p|$ and not $2|p|$ is used.) The problem with $((3))$ is that it breaks space into two regions, but loses the notion of the time separation demonstrated in $((1))$.

Thus there is a problem. One needs two equations and the notion of vector motion as well as incident and reflected/refracted time. Furthermore the equations should apply to a single photon which means time discontinuity.

Single Photon/ Quantum Approach to One Dimensional Reflection/Refraction

The single photon approach shows clearly a discontinuity in time, yet the physics of the problem exists in this scenario. There is no reason to have a continuous steady state beam. Thus the Newtonian idea of smoothness in time does not seem to hold for a single photon. This smoothness is directly linked to velocity i.e. $x=vt$. Thus it is this equation which does not hold. If there is no smoothness in time, $x=vt$ cannot be replaced with another deterministic equation linking x and t because this would also be smooth.. It seems one needs a probabilistic approach which applies non-smoothness in both space and time (because time and space are on a similar footing). In such a case, given that the problem takes place in space, one might try to consider discontinuities in space which remove time in the sense of $x=vt$ i.e. allow it to be discontinuous, i.e. a probability distribution in x with time removed. On average, however, the order of time i.e. incident \rightarrow reflected/refracted still holds and the notion of vector direction must also hold. Furthermore, there must be two equations.

the notion of velocity does not hold (i.e. time is removed from a wavelength leading to the notion of time discontinuity) then the notion of pressure no longer holds because it involves velocity. Impulse, however, should still remain.

To describe this situation one may first write a kind of probability equation:

$$A = |B| + C \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } A, |B|, C \text{ are all } >0 \text{ and } A > C \text{ for } n_1 < n_2 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) has the appearance of a probability equation, but $A, |B|$ and C will be found to be the square root of fluxes/intensity. We note that ((4)) indicates grouping by time i.e. the incident photon on the left and the reflected "or" refracted on the right. Thus the "+" represents probability.

A second equation should indicate impulse i.e. p and demonstrate vector directions without destroying the notion of time grouping:

$$Ap = -p|B| + p^2C \quad ((5))$$

Thus one sees that a reflected beam is associated with $-p$, yet the time grouping still holds, unlike the pressure balance equation ((3)). Let us now call: $B = -|B|$. Then:

$$A+B = C \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad Ap - pB = p^2C \quad ((6b))$$

Multiplying the two equations together yields:

$$AAp - BBp = CCp^2 \quad ((7))$$

((7)), however, is of the form of ((3)) the pressure balance equation which becomes an energy conservation equation when one moves $-BBp$ to the RHS. By multiplying two equations together, one obviously obtains one equation, but the notion of vector directions and time grouping present in ((6b)) now becomes one piece of information, namely either time grouping { ((7)) rearranged to become or vector direction ((7))

The reason that one piece of information is lost is that in order to establish a difference of squares result ((7)) one must group ((6a)) and ((6h)) by space, thus breaking symmetry by choosing a specific grouping. Grouping by time yields:

$$p_{AA} = -p_{BB} = p^2 C|B| - pC|B| + p^2 CC \quad ((8))$$

Thus grouping information is lost as well one equation in order to obtain a Newtonian smooth equation. One sees that one moves from weights A,B,C (with B<0 in the space grouping) to AA,BB,CC which are guaranteed to be positive. Thus there are two sets of probabilities in the picture namely, AA,BB,CC (classical) and A,B,C with BM<0 in the quantum.

Breaking of Time/Space Grouping Symmetry

One may note that in the Newtonian picture of pressure, one must specifically deal with spatial grouping because one deals with force balance. This is done by considering a steady state scenario i.e. one in which one does not need to worry about time. A classical statistical mechanical gas is another example of steady state. Alternatively, energy conservation in a process involves grouping by time. The problem is that in the reflection/refraction problem, using Newtonian notions of velocity and pressure does allow one to have both space and time grouping together. It is one or the other applied to a single equation.

Analogy with the Wavefunction $W(x)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$

The ideas associated with reflection/refraction are also found in the standard wavefunction approach. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ contains two x-probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ indicating the removal of time or time discontinuity, but the two dimensions ensure that the two probabilities combine (through the modulus) to create smooth Newtonian behaviour or $P(x)=1$. $P(x)$ is thus the classical result while $W(x)$ is an averaged square root flux type of probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the one dimensional reflection/refraction problem should be solvable at the single photon level. This, however, implies a discontinuity in time because a single photon either reflects or refracts, yet one requires an equation which includes the incident, reflected and refracted beams together. To create time discontinuity one may consider a probabilistic distribution in x (actually two in two dimensions) such that their modulus equals 1. In such a case $x=vt$ is a kind of averaging result which smoothes over the actual wavelength in the picture. The x-probability picture removes time so there is no notion of pressure either, only impulse. Thus for a single photon one may consider a probability type balance and an impulse balance at $x=0$ the media interface. Both of these equations respect time grouping, while the second also shows vector directions. Given that there are two equations, one may solve for B,C in terms of A:

$$A = |B| + C \quad \text{and} \quad pA = -p|B| + p_2 C \quad ((9))$$

One may next ask: What happens in the steady stream scenario which does not have any time discontinuity? In such a picture fluxes must appear, but time grouping/space grouping symmetry is broken. One either has time grouping i.e. incident flux/c1 = reflected flux/c1 + refracted flux/c2 (energy conservation) or spatial grouping (pressure balance) incident flux p - reflected flux p = refracted flux p2 ((10)).

How is this symmetry broken going from ((9)) to ((10)), i.e. from an impulse with no velocity picture to a Newtonian pressure picture? In order to create a difference of squares picture, ((9)) must be written in a spatial grouping form (i.e. the time grouping is broken). One then obtains $pA - pB = p_2 C$. One may rearrange this to show time only grouping, but one cannot have both together as in ((9)). Thus one loses information moving to a Newtonian smooth $x=vt$ picture i.e. one in which one considers fluxes given by velocity.